

AIEOU
AI IN EDUCATION

DEPARTMENT OF
EDUCATION

UNIVERSITY OF
OXFORD

2025 Annual Report

Prepared By :

Dr Sara Ratner

Professor Rebecca Williams

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About Us

AIEOU was launched in December 2024 and is housed in the Department of Education at the University of Oxford. AIEOU was the brainchild of Dr Sara Ratner who sought to establish an interdisciplinary research hub that would bring together academics, educators, students, technologists, policy makers and others to collaboratively address the challenges being presented by AI in Education. Supported by her colleagues, Professor Rebecca Williams (Law) and Professor Elizabeth Wonnacott (Language Sciences), the Hub was launched with funding from the Social Sciences Division.

“We believe that the Department of Education at the University of Oxford is the natural home for AIEOU as it seeks to convene global experts in the field of AI and Education from across the University and beyond to exchange knowledge and collaborate on learner-centred AI projects.”

Professor Victoria Murphy
Director, Department of Education

Our Vision

AI in Education at Oxford University (AIEOU) seeks to cultivate an interdisciplinary hub that advances a research-informed, ethical, and human-centred approach to artificial intelligence in education. Its vision is to support the diverse needs of global educational communities by fostering collaboration, nurturing knowledge exchange, and enabling responsible innovation that strengthens learning, teaching, and educational systems worldwide.

Research Themes

1

The **DESIGN** of AI for education.

2

The **REGULATION** of AI in education.

3

The **IMPLEMENTATION** of AI in education.

4

The **IMPACT** of AI on education.

Our Team

Professor Rebecca Williams
Co-Investigator

Dr Sara Ratner
Principal Investigator

Professor Elizabeth Wonnacott
Co-Investigator

Dongxia Nie
Research Assistant
Department of Education

Pro Vice Chancellor (Digital) Professor Anne Trefethen

We are grateful to Anne for her leadership, mentorship and expert guidance during the first year of AIEOU.

AIEOU

When we founded AI in Education at Oxford University (AIEOU), I had a feeling the name we chose would make people pause.

English speakers in particular seem unable to resist reordering the letters back into the familiar A E I O U. This was intentional.

The name was inspired not only by our home at Oxford but also by the children's song in which those vowels carry the earliest rhythms of language. They are the quiet scaffolding beneath expression, connection, and understanding, repeated in classrooms across generations. By gently rearranging them and placing AI first, we invite a moment of pause. Just as Generative AI is prompting all of us to reconsider what we believe we understand about how learning unfolds and the purpose of education.

One of our collaborators, Dr Vuyokazi Mntuyedwa from South Africa, recently told us that the majority of her first-year students had never touched a computer before arriving at university. Determined to support them, she began designing a digital literacy course but needed guidance. Through AIEOU she connected with colleagues in Türkiye, India, and the UAE who offered ideas, resources, and steady encouragement. A local challenge became a shared global effort, sustained not by obligation but by generosity.

Stories like this remind us that education is shaped by cultural, relational, institutional, and technological layers that intersect in ways we cannot always predict. AIEOU honours those layers. We do not simply exchange information, we cultivate relationships between educators and technologists, researchers and policymakers, early-career scholars and senior leaders. The Hub is a place where people can think aloud, test ideas, and remain grounded in the human dimensions of a rapidly changing field.

AIEOU is a reminder that even small shifts, like the rearrangement of familiar vowels, can carry profound meaning. It invites us to rethink what we know and reflect on what comes next.

“Encountering AIEOU felt like discovering a busy beehive, alive with purpose. Ideas cross-pollinate and new insights take root. It is a place where people can speak openly about their fears and hopes for AI in education.”

Selin Erzin, United Arab Emirates

Our First Year

AIEOU commenced in December 2024 with a group of 30 committed academics.

As at 12th December 2025 we've welcomed ~3000 collaborators from more than 100 countries.

Our Hub has grown organically as those who collaborate with us share their stories via social media and within their professional networks. We are grateful to every person who has helped build the momentum in support of this vital work. Whilst our focus may be AI, it is the people we work with that we value the most. We have met the most incredible people from across the UK and around the world who share in our vision and mission.

The following pages outline some of our key events and achievements in 2025.

Launch of Website

In December 2024 we launched the AIEOU website.

As at 8 December 2025, our website has recorded 108,000 visitors.

<https://aieou.web.ox.ac.uk>

Launch of AIEOU Teams Channel

The Teams channel was launched in January 2024 and currently has 800 registered users. The Teams channel hosts conversations by research stream (Design, Regulation, Implementation and Impact) and by global region (Asia and the Pacific, UK and Europe, Latin America and Caribbean, Middle East and Africa, North America).

Launch of Social Media

Just prior to our conference in September 2025, we launched our social media channels.

We currently have 265 on Instagram and 1,441 in our LinkedIn group.

This is something we envisage to grow over the next 12 months with additional resourcing.

First AIEOU Publication

In March 2025, we published our first joint paper as part of the INTED2025 Conference which outlined our approach to AIEOU.

Ratner, S., Williams, R., & Wonnacott, E. (2025). Exploring AI in education through interdisciplinary collaboration. In INTED2025 Proceedings (pp. 5650-5655). IATED.

AIEOU Blog Post Authors

The AIEOU community has been active in their support of writing blog posts for our website. We are very grateful for their interesting and insightful contributions.

Some of the most read blogs on our site include:

- Which jobs are AI proof?
- AI in School Management: A new era of leadership
- Can AI close the learning gap?
- What do secondary school students think about AI?

AIEOU Online Launch Event

On the 29th April 2025, the digital launch of the AIEOU Hub brought together approximately 600 academics, educators, researchers, policymakers, industry collaborators, and students from around the world. The vibrant atmosphere was fuelled by a live chat brimming with warm greetings from across the globe. Participants also actively connected with one another and exchanged insights on AI in education throughout the event.

Our First Hire

In March 2025 we recruited our first hire, Dongxia Nie. We were overwhelmed by the quantity and calibre of the applications we received. The job advertisement was reposted on LinkedIn more than 100 times and we gratefully received more than 200 applications for the role. Shortlisting was not easy. We completed five interviews and Dongxia was the successful candidate.

UK National Commission for UNESCO Endorsement

In April 2025, the UK National Commission for UNESCO officially endorsed AIEOU for the UNESCO King Hamad Bin Isa Al-Khalifa Prize. In accordance with UNESCO policy, the UK National Commission is able to endorse a maximum of three submissions for this prestigious award. AIEOU was selected through a highly competitive process.

The Commission was impressed by AIEOU's distinguished all-female leadership, interdisciplinary focus and global reach. Overall, the project is deemed to align with UNESCO's global priorities and the theme of this year's prize, demonstrating an outstanding commitment and inclusive approach to preparing learners and teachers for the ethical and responsible use of AI.

Vice-Chancellor's Award: Highly Commended Prize

Dr Sara Ratner was Highly Commended in the 2025 Vice-Chancellor's Breakthrough Researcher Award having only graduated with her PhD from the University of Sydney in June 2024. She is pictured here at the ceremony in the Sheldonian Theatre with the Vice-Chancellor Professor Irene Tracey and at the celebration in the Examination Halls with Pro-Vice-Chancellor (Digital) Professor Anne Trefethen and Chief Diversity Officer, Professor Tim Soutphommasane.

Egrove Park Dinner Presentation

On the 9th September Dr Sara Ratner was invited to address the 2025 InSpires cohort during their residential retreat at Egrove Park.

Meeting with senior leaders from across the University, Sara was invited to share her story and the work of AIEOU.

Central themes of the dinner talk included: re-defining leadership, finding leaders in unexpected places, the value of collaboration and of course, AI in Education.

CONFERENCE INVITATIONS

Throughout 2025, Rebecca, Sara, Liz and Dongxia were invited to speak about AIEOU and our work at conferences and events around the world for which we are grateful.

School visits and events

During the year we were also invited to join many inspiring school events. Lauren Vallely (pictured here) hosted an event for her school staff to support them as they began exploring the potential for AI. Lauren invited us to speak along with other members of her school community and opened the invitation to everyone on the Teams channel who wished to attend. It was great to see AIEOU folks from local schools join.

Oxford - Cambridge Exchange

During this year's Oxford Cambridge Exchange in the Department of Education, Professor Rebecca Williams presented the work of AIEOU alongside Dongxia Nie. The session was very well attended and well received by Education students from both Universities.

Inaugural Convening

From the 15th to 17th September 2025 Oxford was abuzz with the AIEOU Inaugural Convening. Almost 400 collaborators from around the world came together over three days to share their knowledge, research and questions relating to AI in Education. The feedback from the event was overwhelmingly positive and has led to many ongoing collaborative projects.

What I was most impressed with was the collegiality, most noticeably amongst the Oxford staff. I was taken aback by their willingness to help and support each other, to say "let's make it happen". I have attended too many AI conferences if I'm honest, this was by far the best on many levels. You could tell people cared deeply about solving this WICKED problem and harnessing the opportunities. AIEOU was the single most important and impactful work event I've ever attended.

Associate Professor Mark A. Bassett
Academic Lead (Artificial Intelligence)
Deputy Vice-Chancellor (Academic) Portfolio
Charles Sturt University

I lead all things digital for three schools in London. The quality of what I saw and heard in the two days this week was so exceptionally good that it really moved the goalposts on what I will be engaging with in the future. Thank you so much for what is very likely going to be the highlight of this year in professional terms.

Adam Zivanic
Director of Digital Strategy
City Schools, London

The inaugural AIEOU conference brought together a diverse group of academics, educators, policymakers, and industry leaders who were united by a shared goal: to build a map for the future of AI in education through collaboration and thoughtful partnership. What stood out wasn't just the content, it was the emergence of a community that feels intentional. A group focused on designing AI to support meaningful learning, not just commercial success.

Isaac Pattis, Tech Lead, OUP

The beauty of the venue, the thoughtfulness of the programme, and, most of all, the remarkable sense of community you managed to create made this gathering unlike any other. I left Oxford feeling inspired, connected, and hopeful about the future we can shape together. Thank you for the opportunity to be part of something so meaningful.

Joanne Caddy, OECD

Open Access Research Repository

Following the conference presenters were invited to upload their presentation to our open access research repository on Zenodo.

<https://zenodo.org/communities/aieou/>

This repository will house research outputs from our external collaborators across AIEOU for all to access and share.

Conference Abstract Book

The AIEOU 2025 Conference Abstract Book contains more than 100 abstracts from the presentations and posters shared at the inaugural convening in September 2025.

Citation: Nie, D., Williams, R., Wonnacott, E., & Ratner, S. (2025, September 15). AIEOU 2025 Conference Abstract Book. AIEOU Inaugural Conference 2025, University of Oxford. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17601107>

Our Sponsors

AIEOU was established thanks to funding awarded by the Social Sciences Division. We value their support greatly and the efforts of the Divisional staff are very much appreciated. Special thanks to Samantha Harper, Noora Kanfash, Helena Channon-Wells, Alexandru Martalogu and Rebecca Jones.

Conference Sponsors

We are grateful to Oxford University Press who were the sponsors of our inaugural convening. They provided support and collegiality throughout, engaging fully in our shared vision for the importance of this work. Thanks to Sarah Ultsch and everyone at OUP. We loved sharing this experience with you.

Conference Support

Thanks to Caroline Williams and the team at Said Business School.
Thanks to Elizabeth Wonnacott and the events team at St John's College, Oxford.
Thanks to Rebecca Williams, Erika Arnaudo and the events team at Pembroke College.
Thanks to Andrew Serazin, Anthony Brigden and Reuben College.

The GPT
Ginger Beer and Peach Tea

The GBS
Strawberry, Basil and Soda

The LLM
Lime, Lemonade and Mint

The AIEOU
Apple, Ice, Elderflower, Orange soda and an Umbrella

University Council Away Day

On the 26th September 2025, Dr Sara Ratner was invited to present the AIEOU Interdisciplinary Research Hub's work to the University Council at their away day.

The presentation to leaders from across the University of Oxford was very well received and AIEOU received strong support from those in attendance including Professor Tim Powers, Head of the Social Sciences Division.

Vice-Chancellor delivering the Oration Sheldonian Theatre on 7th October 2025.

Vice-Chancellor's Oration

The Vice-Chancellor Professor Irene Tracey CBE FRS FMedSci delivered her annual Oration to the University of Oxford on the 7th October 2025. Dr Sara Ratner was invited to attend the event at the Sheldonian Theatre alongside the incoming Director of the Department of Education, Professor Leon Feinstein and Head of Administration and Finance, Mrs Lesley-Anne Adams.

The Vice-Chancellor's oration provided a clear endorsement of our work, recognising the AI in Education at Oxford University Hub as an example of Oxford's leadership in human-centred AI. Her words remind us that "Hope and kindness are not soft words, but the foundations on which trust and progress are built." This year AIEOU has translated that principle into action by advancing evidence-based practice, shaping policy, and supporting work that puts learners and educators at the centre of design.

Moving forward, we will continue to combine rigorous scholarship with practical collaboration, producing research that informs teaching, and scales our efforts responsibly.

The Vice-Chancellor observed, "As I look ahead, I want Oxford to be remembered not just for what we discovered, taught or built, but for how we did it — with Hope in what is possible, Truth as our North Star and Kindness in our hearts." AIEOU is committed to helping write that story through measured impact, sustained partnerships, and a focus on inclusion, fairness and learning for all.

MIT Day of AI

The AIEOU Leadership team were invited to join MIT Raise at their Global Summit for the Day of AI.

Hosted by DP World in Dubai, the summit brought together policy makers and AI ecosystem builders from across the globe.

From the 17th to 19th November the conversations flowed about the challenges of AI and how schools around the world can best support young people.

Thanks to Day of AI, Ethan Berman and Cynthia Breazeal for their kindness and hospitality in Dubai.

WOMEN IN AI

Professor Liz Wonnacott discussed the role of AI in enhancing human language learning during Expert Series Session 5, hosted by the Global Women in AI Ethics & Culture Office.

Liz has been researching and working in the field of AI and linguistics for quite some time, starting with her first degree in Edinburgh during the 90s.

Oxford Digital Festival

AIEOU was well represented at Oxford's DigiFest on 20th November thanks to Dongxia Nie and Professor Rebecca Williams. Dongxia showcased AIEOU and Rebecca delivered a talk titled, 'Divided by a common language'. Teaching lawyers and computer scientists together, she helps them to understand each others' mindsets and how they can go on to create practical projects together, many with AI.

Webinar Series

Commencing in August 2025, we launched our successful webinar series. People from across our community have shared the knowledge and experience with us. Thank you to everyone who volunteered. The series is scheduled to continue until June 2026.

We have a term card for the 8 weeks of each Oxford term. The webinars are typically scheduled at 10am, 1pm or 5pm UK time to allow for different time zones but of course, it is driven by our speakers availability.

The series is listed on our website and each week we share a reminder on our Teams channel and/or socials.

Attendance ranges from 63 (more intimate, conversation style presentation) to 146 participants per session. Recordings are made available afterwards where possible but this has proven challenging due to our resources. Over the past 5 months, 1142 people have joined one of our webinars.

There is great potential for this series to develop as there is a wealth of talent across our community. There were so many people who volunteered to participate but we only had 24 slots. A goal for 2026 is to secure funding to hire a dedicated team member to support this series. As the series matures we will also explore promoting it more widely. Until now it has been an offering for our AIEOU community.

Global Perspectives

AIEOU was designed as a collaborative interdisciplinary research hub that is open to everyone interested in better understanding the potential and risk of AI in educational contexts. One of the challenges in this work is how to best harness global voices on the topic.

At Oxford we have created the space for these conversations to take place. We do not hold the answers, merely the opportunity to come together to dwell with the complexity of the issue.

How do we best amplify the voices of all learners in this conversation? The challenge is ongoing but we call on our community to generate ideas and suggestions.

In January 2026 we aim to launch the Collab Labs as a means for establishing a shared research agenda and to work together in an effort to answer some of our most pressing questions when it comes to AI in education.

“AIEOU has been an impactful community bringing together numerous nuanced voices from across the globe. The regular interactions on multiple platforms, be it blog, seminar, webinar have not just been interesting but also though provoking. I hope the community soon looks to publish a journal and a podcast. Wishing the community many more years of learning and joy.”

Rahul Pachori, Director, Central India Education Ministry

Coffee Chats

We are honoured to meet and converse with people from around the world. Just some of the inspiring people that have popped in to have a coffee with us in Oxford this year:

Vassa Mustikahati
Expert Advisor to the Minister
in Education & Child Development at
the Coordinating Ministry for Human
Development and Cultural Affairs,
Republic of Indonesia

Chris Bush
Churchill Fellow
Australia

Lydia Foong
Taylor's University
Malaysia

Simon Buckingham Shum

Carla Aerts

Judit Martínez Moreno

Assoc Prof Chua Bee Leng, Assoc Prof Tan Seng Chee, Assoc Prof Chen Wenli
and Asst Prof Edwin Chng from the National Institute of Education (Singapore)

Impact

During our first year we are proud to have played a part in shaping global approaches to AI in Education. There is much work taking place in this space and we are pleased to share a small number of examples that we can share with you here:

Working with Governments

Sara Ratner worked with AIEOU collaborators (Clara Hawking, David Rudd, Julie Foss, Rebecca Pitkin, Mirza Baig, Helen Crompton, Salih Mansur, Aigerim Shilibekova, Jaime Bissa, Naaz Farooqi, Obed Boateng and Hang Vu) to submit a response to the USA White House Request for Public Input on the AI Action Plan. Our submission recognises the essential role of human-centred design in ensuring that AI tools complement rather than replace educators. We advocate for the establishment of coherent legal frameworks so that AI systems are transparent and respectful of learner data. We also encourage greater cross-sector collaboration and professional development so that AI solutions can be implemented responsibly, and we emphasise continuous monitoring to measure whether these technologies truly enhance learning outcomes.

Another key element of our response is the imperative of digital literacy for all members of society, including school leaders, teachers, and policymakers. AI readiness should not be confined to technical experts; it must be woven into educational structures so that future generations can interact confidently and responsibly with advanced technologies. By maintaining this focus on shared knowledge, we aim to nurture an environment in which AI drives genuine innovation and progress while upholding ethical obligations.

Our response is published on the US Government's website and is well represented in the plan.

We have also engaged in high level conversations with DSIT (UK), DfE (UK), Indonesia, Singapore, Malaysia, South Korea, Taiwan, Vietnam, Kazakhstan, Türkiye and Canada.

Working with Tech

Members of the AIEOU leadership team have been invited to roundtables and conversations with tech providers to brief them on human-centred AI approaches that meet the needs and concerns of our community.

This year we were invited to events and closed door meetings with Google Deepmind, Google for Education, OpenAI and Microsoft along with those hosted by start ups and mid-scale tech companies. Leaning in to these conversations enables us to understand the implications of this technology better and brings the voice of the AIEOU community to the design of AI for education.

Working with Policy

The AIEOU leadership team has joined working groups to support the development of University policy on the use of 'Generative AI in Research' and on the 'Ethics Review of AI Research'. The policy work led by Lotte Boon is now live on the University of Oxford website and the paper, first authored by Angeliki Kerasidou has been accepted for publication in Research Ethics journal.

Where to next?

AIEOU has a clear vision, strong momentum and the desire to make a positive impact.

As a next step, AIEOU is seeking large-scale funding partners and support to establish itself further as a global research hub for AI in Education. We have the vision, the momentum and the urgent need to make this happen.

We are also partnering to fund opportunities for students to undertake research degrees at the University of Oxford and look forward to welcoming the next generation of AIED scholars to lead us into the future.

The first steps have been taken to launch the AIEOU Collab Labs and that will be our focus in 2026 as we work to provide educators and learners around the world with the evidence they need to truly understand the potential impact of AI.

Thank You

Finally and most importantly, an enormous thank you to our AIEOU community and to everyone at the University of Oxford who has supported our efforts over the past 12 months. 2025 has been amazing thanks to all of you. Looking forward to 2026.

It seems fitting to end this report with the words of our AIEOU community, some of whom have shared their first birthday wishes on the following pages!

Sara, Becca, Liz and Dongxia

Happy Birthday AIEOU!

Happy birthday AIEOU!

Thank you all for fostering inclusive conversations and projects!

Maud Stiernet, UK and Europe

Celebrating the first birthday of AIEOU Hub feels special because this space has genuinely shaped my journey. What I value most is the way it brings people together across countries. We meet, collaborate and actually understand each other's work, which is rare and refreshing. Being part of AIEOU has also pushed me to go deeper into AI and its impact on education. I've grown simply because the community keeps nudging me to explore more. And honestly, the team's energy makes all the difference. Their constant involvement adds a kind of zeal that keeps the whole hub alive and moving ❤️ Best wishes to Sara, team and all members associated with AIEOU.

Dr Deepika Kohli, Asia and Oceania

Although I am still very new to this community, AIEOU has already given me something invaluable, which is the feeling that I am not alone in caring deeply about the human side of education in the AI-driven age. AIEOU reflects what I have always admired about Oxford: the university's acceptance, sense of depth, curiosity, and a space where people think together for a purpose bigger than themselves. The community has shown me that when people come together with care, honesty and a shared mission, we can navigate the opportunities and risks of AI in Education with humanity at its core. This hub is a testament that, despite innovations, core human values can be acknowledged and preserved.

I am grateful to be here, and I hope this hub continues to grow, connect people across the world, and continue to make a real impact in the years ahead.

Arwa Taibani, Asia and Oceania

In just one year, AIEOU has become a powerful space where educators, researchers, and innovators collaborate to shape responsible AI in education. Happy to be here.

Ishak Kirac, UK and Europe

It has been wonderful connecting with so many inspiring people in the AIEOU community who share similar concerns about AI in Education. I am grateful for this first year together and excited for many more to come!

Nermin Karademir, UK and Europe

Human connection in the age of AI is vital now more than ever by connecting real research, practical advice and sharing these are critical for global adoption and efficacy of AI in education

Dan Bowen, Australia

Wishing AIEOU a very happy birthday!

I wish the whole big family of AIEOU many more years of success and prosperity!

Shakhnoza Mustanova, Asia and Oceania

Congratulations to AIEOU team led by Dr. Sara Ratner for supporting this and to the entire community for the work and knowledge sharing they have shown to be possible. Paul Edelblut, Americas

Such a great community! I'm glad I met you 🤝

Şenda Yıldırım Çelik, Middle East

This is an amazing initiative which has enabled us researchers in establishing a clearer focus around the use of AI in education.

Vasiliki Kontou, UK and Europe

Thank you so much, Sara, Rebecca, Liz and Dongxia, for your incredible commitment. Grateful to be part of the AIEOU Research Community & excited for the year ahead!

Christine Stoltz, UK and Europe

Congratulations AIEOU! Your continued commitment to advancing responsible and equitable AI in Education sets an inspiring standard for researchers and practitioners worldwide. Subhra Shankha Chakraborty, Asia and Oceania

Happy Birthday AIEOU!

What inspires me the most is how a range of professionals are working together without any monetary reward - everyone wants to work on this and achieve and the mutual respect, enthusiasm and drive towards ensuring we provide the best outcomes for our students and pupils is something to be proud of.

Lauren Valley, UK and Europe

Happy first birthday, AIEOU! ❤️

In just one year, you've given me so many gifts: new friends, shared visions, and bright collaborations. You brought Mel, Rachel, the Australian team, Sara, the whole AIEOU team, and so many other scholars into my world. 🌍 Because of you, the journey into the AI future feels more human, lit with the warmth of shared purpose. 🎉

Gloria Alpini, UK and Europe

The growth of the AIEOU this past year has been amazing to watch, both in how it's spotlighting important work in AI and education, and in the way it genuinely brings people together from across the globe.

Working in AI at Oxford, I've seen firsthand how this field creates communities where we exchange knowledge and build skills together, but the AIEOU amplifies all of that on an international scale. It's already having a real impact in my work: I'm developing a major project that grew directly from a connection I made at the AIEOU conference.

That's the power of this community - human connection that is creating opportunities for collaboration that wouldn't exist otherwise.

Kelly Webb-Davies, UK and Europe

Happy birthday ❤️

Zeynep Öztürk Duman

AIEOU helped move the question from "what can AI do?" to "how do we integrate it responsibly across the whole ecosystem?" That shift matters. Grateful for the learning, the partnerships, and the sharing. Thanks to the amazing team for convening a thoughtful, values-driven community.

Prem Radhakrishnan, Australia

AIEOU gave me a sense of community at a time when the field moves fast and feels overwhelming. I learned a lot from the discussions, and it pushed me to think bigger about how AI can support children's learning.

Lilia Dabija, UK and Europe

Being a member of AIEOU has been truly impactful, especially in broadening my global perspective on AI in Education and helping refine policy thinking. The webinars and forum discussions are consistently insightful, and the research papers shared by fellow members have been particularly valuable. This is an excellent initiative and kudos to the entire team for the meaningful work you continue to drive.

Gowri Shankar Sivabala, Middle East

AIEOU has reminded me how transformative it can be when a community comes together to reimagine learning through collaboration and innovation. I'm happy to be connected with educators from all around the world who are exploring and shaping the future of AI in education. Happy birthday, here's to many more years of learning and growing together!

Ebru Karayel Çınar

Happy Birthday AIEOU!

AIEOU may be only a year old, yet it already feels like the vowel set shaping a new language for AI in education.

“Curiosity × Collaboration × Courage” has become the defining equation of this community, giving structure and coherence to its emerging discourse.

My sincere thanks to Dr. Sara Ratner and the team for their thoughtful leadership and for cultivating a community that speaks with clarity and purpose.

Happy Birthday, AIEOU! Here is to many years ahead as we continue developing the grammar, the syntax, and the full vocabulary of this shared work!

Aigerim “Aia” Shilibekova, Americas

Happy first birthday to AIEOU! What an exciting milestone for a community that is already shaping the future of AI in Education. This is only the beginning of what I believe will be an important journey for educators, students, and the broader learning ecosystem. A huge congratulations to Sara and the entire AIEOU team. Their leadership, vision, and hard work have driven remarkable achievements in just one year. I look forward to seeing the continued impact they will make as they support and inspire educators around the world.

Vishal Rana, Middle East

It's inspiring to see how this community continues to grow, connect, and shape the future of AI in education. I'm proud and deeply grateful to be part of this journey. Thank you for creating a space where meaningful collaboration, curiosity, and innovation can flourish. Happy birthday!

Christa Schmid-Meier, UK and Europe

Thank you so much for everything you are doing. Yonak Welker, Middle East

As a Computer Sciences lecturer, AIEOU has been an incredible source of inspiration for adapting my curriculum to the AI era. Happy 1st Birthday to this amazing global community.

AFRA NUR VATANSEVER, Middle East

I'm grateful for the collaborations, insights, and shared commitment to building ethical and human-centred learning futures. Happy first birthday!

Mustafa TUĞYAN, Middle East

Happy anniversary, AIEOU! It's inspiring to see how your work continues to support educators and learners. Here's to many more years of innovation and growth!

Salvatore Varriale

AIEOU was the community I needed at this stage of my career, with what is being achieved in this community, I will be part of this highly intellectual, vibrant, inclusive, and truly global community always.

Zaheed Mahmood, UK and Europe

AIEOU has been one of the most diverse and open communities in AI and education out there, which is free from siloes and institutional barriers. I'm so happy to be a member of this community!

Joseph Marvin Imperial, UK and Europe

My experience with AIEOU addresses current educational tensions: leveraging AI's potential while preserving human-centered learning. As I grapple with ethical innovation in AI integration, the AIEOU community has sustained me through genuine human connection. These relationships demonstrate that the path forward requires collective wisdom. I am deeply grateful for the AIEOU partners and friends I have found on this journey.

Rachel Toncelli, Americas

Being part of AIEOU journey has been a privilege. Your dedication to advancing education, empowering learners, and uplifting our community is truly inspiring.

Nurkhamimi Zainuddin, Asia and Oceania

Happy Birthday AIEOU!

AIEOU has become a platform where people from all over the world can exchange ideas, research, and experiences related to AI. It connects teachers and scholars all over the world, and thus serves as a unique space where global opinions, contributions to science and practice reach people faster than ever! Thank you very much for establishing such a platform and uniting so many people from around the globe!! Shakhnoza Mustanova

AIEOU is heaving of intellectual vibe and energetic desire to make a positive impact. The richness of expertise and experience is unparalleled and tremendously effective.

Marco Mongiello, UK and Europe

Global leadership in a time of pressing need to understand and re-invent academia in the age of AI.

Daswin De Silva, Asia and Oceania

I am grateful to Oxford and the AIEOU team for creating a community that is open, reflective and genuinely focused on learners and teachers, not just technology.
Stamatios Papadakis, Europe

What stands out is not just the conversations AIEOU has started, but the community it has built, one that is genuinely collaborative, globally minded, and grounded in practice. I am excited to see how this work continues to shape thinking, research, and action in the years ahead. Congratulations on an outstanding first year!
Samantha Curle, UK and Europe

I'm grateful to be part of this academic community. The support, collaboration, and inspiration I've found here have shaped my growth as both a scholar and an educator. Happy birthday and here's to many more years of learning and innovation together!
Beyza Yilmaz, Americas

AIEOU stands as a truly global platform that has transformed the way educators, researchers, and policymakers connect and collaborate in the field of AI and education. At the heart of this impactful initiative is Dr Sara Ratner, whose visionary leadership and steadfast dedication were instrumental in shaping this research ecosystem. Ozel Hurmuzlu, Middle East

Being part of AIEOU has connected our work with inspiring educators and innovators around the world. Together, we are using AI and international collaboration to promote greater equity and opportunity in global education.

Shaofeng Wang, UK and Europe

Being part of the AIEOU community has significantly enriched my professional growth. The insights, collaboration, and shared purpose have strengthened my work and broadened our perspective. I am grateful for the opportunity to engage, learn, and contribute. Thank you for creating a space where voices are valued. This platform has played a meaningful role in my development, offering learning, dialogue, and inspiration that shape my work as an educator and leader providing an opportunity to network. I really appreciate the opportunity to express my views and be part of such an impactful initiative. Thank you for your commitment and for welcoming our contributions. I look forward to continued collaboration and future milestones together with AIEOU. Aarti Sharma, Africa

Being part of this community has been an inspiring journey. The collaborative spirit, innovation, and shared passion for shaping the future of AI in Education have truly enriched my learning and professional growth. I'm grateful for the connections, insights, and opportunities this community has created, and I look forward to many more years of collective impact.

Mubarak AbdulSalam, Middle East

Cheers to AIEOU's first birthday!

Wishing more years of continued success!
Ryan Dave Delos Reyes, Asia and Oceania

Happy Birthday AIEOU!

Knowing that you walk this unknown path with others is empowering and supportive in the most profound way. Chris Bush, Asia and Oceania

It will forever remain one of the most formative experiences of my professional life. THANK YOU!
Lee Barrett, Asia and Oceania

Being part of AIEOU has expanded not only my understanding of AI in education, but also the collective vision we share for transforming learning worldwide. This community inspires collaboration, elevates our thinking, and reminds us that the future of education is one we build together. Alejandra Clerici Arias, Americas

It truly value being part of AIEOU and really look forward to building more collaborations in the future. This AIEOU community inspires me to keep learning and exploring how AI can transform education.
Gumrah Sahin, UK and Europe

Being part of this community shows how education keeps evolving through curiosity, kindness, and shared creativity. Celebrating the first year means celebrating everyone who contributes ideas, questions, and enthusiasm. Here's to more learning, more collaboration, and a future where knowledge stays open to all!
Tobias Morat, UK and Europe

Happy Blrthday! You are the best.
Merve Bako, UK and Europe

AIEOU is a truly global learning family. In just one year, it has inspired collaboration, thoughtful debate, and responsible innovation in AI and education. I am proud to be part of this journey and deeply appreciate the openness, warmth, and intellectual energy that AIEOU brings to the international academic community.
Bharat Singh Deora, Asia and Oceania

AIEOU is a community that has helped to keep myself updated with new Educational research and create meaningful connection with lots of Educators around the world.
Judith Marcelo, UK and Europe

I love being part of the AIEOU Community!
Raona Williams, Middle East

Being part of this team feels like standing at the edge of the future with people who dare to reimagine it. Here, ideas spark, perspectives shift, and possibilities expand. I believe the work we will create together can illuminate entirely new paths for the world.
Melisa Gülfem Başer, Middle East

Thank you sincerely AIEOU for your energy, commitment, and dedication to advancing meaningful change in education. Whilst we are often characterised as slow to innovate and reactive by nature, the AIEOU team has led a community that defies this perception, demonstrating that education can be at the forefront of transformation. It is a privilege to be part of such a positive movement.
Antoine Casanova-Mazet, UK and Europe

Happy Birthday! It has been incredible to witness the advancements you've made. Your dedication to fostering innovation and knowledge is truly inspiring, and I look forward to supporting your community's growth for many years to come!
Zeynep Kumkale, UK and Europe

Happy Birthday AIEOU!

Being part of this community has been one of the most inspiring parts of my journey. Together, we're not just following the future of education — we're building it. Happy birthday, and here's to many more years of growth, innovation, and shared success!

Mustafa HASTÜRK, Middle East

It has been brilliant to collaborate through the AIEOU, meeting new colleagues and sharing ideas. Joe Cozens, UK and Europe

Delighted to share my experience with AIEOU! As a researcher passionate about leveraging AI for social good, I'm impressed by the hub's work on AI in education. It's research and resources are helping shape the future of learning, making it more inclusive and effective. Here's to many more years of innovation and impact!

Noor Aisha, Asia and Oceania

What an incredible community to be a part of. Passionate, positive and inspiring springs to mind! Led by a great time and involving experts from around the world. It's a true honour to be a part of something so important and special.

Faye Waterton-Palmer, UK and Europe

Thanks for all the amazing opportunities and people.

Taylor Azola, UK and Europe

I am always grateful to be part of AIEOU, a community that brings together professionals from diverse backgrounds and gives ideas the space to grow. Although I joined later, it is hard to believe a year has already passed. Indeed, it feels like the beginning of something meaningful and promising. I've had an opportunity to experience Oxford's culture, be surrounded by esteemed scholars, leaders and practitioners from a wide range of disciplines, explore their work, learn, help and expand my skills and perspective. My sincere thanks go to Sara Ratner whose leadership continues to set an example and the team for fostering a collaborative, respectful, and genuinely supportive environment. The thoughtful content and well-designed events both online and in person have created a space where learning feels purposeful and shared. I look forward to collaborating and becoming even more involved in the work that makes this community so special.

Ece Yavuzarslan, Asia and Oceania

Happy Birthday AIEOU!

Olga, UK and Europe

I believe AI in Education initiative at Oxford University is creating a lasting change not only on individuals in the field, but entire institutions through its dynamic hub and this transformation ultimately improves the learning experiences of teachers and students across the globe. Shawana Fazal, Asia and Oceania

Happy Birthday AIEOU! 🎉

You continue to inspire creativity, learning, and smiles every single day. Wishing you more success, more joy, and many more years of bringing people together. Cheers to a wonderful journey ahead! 🥳👉

Muhammad Abdullah Kamran

AIEOU has created a truly vibrant space for meaningful dialogue and collaboration in AI in Education. I am grateful to be part of this growing global community.

Gyanendra Rawat

I am proud to be part of this community and look forward to seeing AIEOU's impact on AI-driven education grow even stronger each year.

Ali Batuhan Yıldız

The AIEOU is a lighthouse in the fog of AI-in-education noise.

Mark Barrett, Asia and Oceania

Happy Birthday AIEOU!

Great to be part of this community! Cintia Pla-García , UK and Europe

Being part of AIEOU has felt like stepping into a world where ideas move faster than time. The webinars sharpened my technical toolkit and gave me a clear framework for turning ideas into reproducible experiments. The recent webinar on Integrating Generative AI and Universal Design for Learning, for example, was a turning point. This webinar leveraged GenAI to enhance and scale the implementation of the core UDL principles. Armed with this new knowledge, I returned to my role as Research Director at the Generative Artificial Intelligence for Education and Research in Africa (GenAI-ERA) hub with renewed confidence. Suddenly, complex generative AI concepts became tools I could wield with precision. I led my team through innovative projects, introduced smarter workflows, and built systems that once felt out of reach. Our hub began producing insights that attracted collaborators, funding, and recognition. The success wasn't accidental, it was the direct result of immersing myself in a community that pushed the frontier of AI in education. The AIEOU Interdisciplinary Research Hub didn't just teach me; it elevated me. And in turn, I elevated the work of everyone I led at the GenAI-ERA hub. Patrick Kyeremeh, Africa.

Incredible first year for AIEOU!

A truly global community, thoughtful conversations, and an inaugural conference that was welcoming, energizing, and expertly planned!
Casandra Silva Sibilin, Americas

Oxford has played a highly impactful role by establishing AIEOU as a credible and truly global community. Its academic reputation, convening power, and commitment to open dialogue have created a trusted space where researchers, practitioners, and policymakers from diverse regions can come together to critically and collaboratively explore the opportunities and challenges of AI in Education. Oxford's leadership has not only provided intellectual direction but has also fostered inclusivity, interdisciplinary exchange, and global reach, which are essential for meaningful progress in this field.

Murat Kurt, Middle East

Our collaboration with AIEOU has been one of the most meaningful experiences of my professional journey. It gave me not just a platform but a community, a space where creativity, compassion and courage truly come alive. We had the privilege of presenting our paper in Oxford and the University gave us a sense of belonging. Standing in a place that has shaped generations of thinkers was profoundly emotional. The conversations, the recognition and the supportive academic environment moved us in ways that will stay with us forever. All thanks to Sara, who made these experiences come alive and even more special. Her warmth, encouragement and unwavering belief in collaborative innovative inspired us deeply and strengthened our own sense of purpose. With AIEOU, We felt seen, valued and empowered to dream bigger.

Rashee Singh and Prachya Prerna, Asia

Happy Birthday! It has been so incredible to see the impact this has in connecting people globally to engage in AI in education and in such a short space of time! Excited to see the next stage as research and connections begin to embed and flourish.

Helen Pepper, UK and Europe

Congratulations, AIEOU, and thank you. This group has opened up my professional world in ways that range from broadened perspective and opportunity to exposure to content I didn't realize was out there. Julie Foss, Americas

Happy Birthday AIEOU!

AIEOU has been a genuinely inspiring and intellectually generous community. It brings together researchers, educators, and practitioners from around the world to think with one another rather than in silos. For me, AIEOU has provided not only visibility for my work in AI-supported learning and cognition, but also a sense of shared purpose—reminding us that the future of AI in Education should be shaped collaboratively, critically, and ethically. Happy first birthday to a community that embodies openness, curiosity, and global dialogue.

Huiwen Wang, UK and Europe

As a doctoral student at Oxford, the AIEOU enhances participation and allows connection to the wider AI community with a shared interest in education, and discussion of how this new industrial revolution can best impact the future.

Alan Potts, UK and Europe

The convening remains a special memory for me. For my first conference as a researcher, I could not have asked for a warmer reception, a more diverse range of presentations or a nicer cohort.

William Porter, UK and Europe

Being part of AIEOU has been one of the most inspiring and intellectually enriching experiences of my academic journey. It is a rare community where curiosity, critical inquiry, and human-centred innovation truly come together. AIEOU has not only expanded how I think about AI in education, but has also connected me with remarkable scholars who challenge, support, and energize my work. I am grateful for the opportunity to learn, contribute, and grow alongside such a visionary network. Happy birthday, AIEOU. Here's to many more years of shaping the future of learning with purpose and integrity.

Ozlem Zengin

Wonderful job everyone. Truly grateful to be part of AIEOU.

Jinu K Varghese, Asia and Oceania

It's great to be part of AIEOU knowing we are all impacting change small or big for the greater good of the Education Global Landscape. Thank you. Happy Birthday!

Hafiza Rasool, UK and Europe

Thank you for this wonderful community!

Natalia Kurcikova, UK and Europe

The AIEOU community has been invaluable in building global connections with others in education.

Lori Robbins, Americas

AIEOU gave me a space to grow with others who care about using AI to make learning simpler and more human.

Salih Mansur, Americas

Happy birthday, what a beautiful first year. The AIEOU team should be very proud of the network and legacy they have created.

Lucy Read, UK and Europe

Happy FIRST to AIEOU! Thank you for bringing together such a vibrant community of learners. Proud to be part of this journey.

Meena Kapahi

AIEOU provides a positive path through a potentially fraught future.

Annette Rome, Asia and Oceania

AIEOU has become a truly inspiring hub for exploring how AI can meaningfully transform teaching and learning. Over the past year, it has brought educators, researchers, and innovators together to build a future where AI enhances not replaces human creativity, critical thinking, and learner autonomy. As someone working in English language education, I deeply value AIEOU's commitment to ethical, inclusive, and research-informed innovation. Congratulations on your first birthday, and thank you for leading such an important movement in AI and education!

Sisay Bezabih, Africa

Happy Birthday AIEOU!

I am happy to celebrate the first anniversary of the AIEOU! Since its launch, AIEOU has established itself as a global platform that contributes to the future of education driven by research-informed, ethical and human-centered principles. As a collaborator, I was proud to contribute to the inaugural meeting in September 2025, where I shared insights on the critical need for responsible AI solutions and 'Purpose-First' instead of 'AI-first' mindset. The Hub's interdisciplinary work across its four foundational pillars of Design, Regulation, Implementation and Impact, is important for the future where educational institutions and internal stakeholders are the main drivers of healthy, sustainable and human-driven educational ecosystems. Congratulations with a phenomenal first year of impact! 🎉

Tatjana Titareva, UK and Europe

AIEOU connected me with people whose ideas fundamentally shifted the way I think about learning and AI. Each conversation sparked a new direction; each collaboration unlocked a new horizon. This community has become one of the most meaningful intellectual ecosystems in my professional journey.

Ilker Ulubey, UK and Europe

My 2025 year highlight: attending the inaugural AIEOU conference at Oxford. Presenting my thoughts, connecting with inspiring leaders, and being part of this community was incredible. Thank you Sara Rathner and the team for bringing us together. Noosha Mehdian, Americas

An excellent initiative which is changing engagement and research projects positively!

John Kennedy, UK and Europe

The amount of work within a year has been astonishing - AIEOU has been represented in Policy papers at national and international levels, as well as hosting and participating in several conferences. The first annual conference in Oxford itself was incredibly well curated and I learned so much from and with other people I met at the event. It's a lot of work, more than I can appreciate, but I hope you're able to keep this up well into the future. David Nally, Asia and Oceania

AIEOU has connected me with a vibrant network of educators and researchers who are shaping the future of AI in education with accessibility in mind.

Estella Oncins, UK and Europe

Sara's idea for AIEOU, born of passion and purpose, has travelled the globe like a bolt of lightning, with incredible impact and speed. So amazing to witness, and an honour to be part of the journey. Congratulations to all!

Kate Arthur, Americas

Many thanks to all the AIEOU staff for the invaluable work done so far... the best is yet to come! 😊

Mirko Susta, UK and Europe

Happy birthday to this amazing community! Keep shining, keep growing, keep inspiring.

Meenakshi Dwivedi, Asia and Oceania

Happy birthday, AIEOU! I'm so grateful to be part of this incredible global organization. Here's to even more impact in 2026!

Ilka Kosta, Americas

The work that this group is doing is so very valuable. Luke Harris, UK

Happy 1 year, AIEOU! Thanks for bringing together such an amazing international community.

Meghan Killeen, Americas.

Happy Birthday AIEOU!

AIEOU provides a unique environment where a shared vision is enriched by a chorus of diverse perspectives. The fusion of academics, educators, and industry experts creates a dynamic ecosystem of learning and growth.

My active participation in AIEOU hub activities including responding to the US Federal Government's RFI, presenting at the inaugural conference, engaging in webinars has provided me with valuable opportunities. Warmest wishes to AIEOU and everyone on this shared journey of learning!

Naaz Farooqi, UK and Europe

AIEOU connected me with a vibrant community of researchers who share my passion for AI in Education. It encourages fresh ideas and meaningful discussions while bringing people together from all over the world. As a global field, AI in Education relies on a collaborative environment, one that AIEOU effectively provides to help us move forward. Thank you for letting me be part of that!

Sofia Aparicio, Americas

Happy first birthday, AIEOU! I value this collaboration as it allowed me to contribute a South African perspective to a global dialogue on responsible AI in Education. It reinforced the principle that teaching and learning must remain at the centre of every technological advancement. I value the community Sara and the AIEOU team have built. It creates space for rigorous thinking and shared growth across diverse contexts. Wishing AIEOU a strong first birthday and continued growth in knowledge and impact.

Elizabeth Booi, Africa

Congrats to the AIEOU team. A thriving community has been created! Please organise another conference as soon as possible!

Les Hopper, UK and Europe

Happy birthday to an inspiring community! Your dedication to thoughtful, human-centred teaching and learning is a gift to everyone around you. Here's to many more years of growth and impact!

Fatemeh Ranjbaran Madiseh, Middle East

It has been wonderful to connect and explore questions while we live out this paradigm shift.

Alison Galia Gonzalez, Asia and Oceania

Shout out to everyone involved. You have truly created a movement that is hard to ignore. Chris Foltz, Americas

AIEOU has become one of the most important voices shaping the future of AI in education. In just one year, it has brought together researchers, practitioners, and innovators who share a bold vision: that AI should empower learners, elevate teachers, and expand opportunities for every student, no matter their background or context.

Being part of this community has inspired my own work on equitable AI literacy and shown me what is possible when thoughtful research, ethical leadership, and educational passion come together. Congratulations to AIEOU on an extraordinary first year, I can't wait to see the impact we create together in the next.

Remi Momo, UK and Europe

Happy Birthday AIEOU!

Education does not advance through novelty alone. It advances through institutions willing to ask hard questions, hold the line on rigour, and place human development at the center of innovation.

What the Oxford Department of Education has done consistently is create space for serious thinking in an age that often prefers speed over substance. At a moment when AI, data, and technology are rushing into classrooms faster than evidence can keep up, Oxford has remained a place where trust, ethics, and learning science are treated as infrastructure, not afterthoughts. That leadership matters. Not just to researchers, but to every educator and student whose future depends on getting this right.

Happy birthday, and thank you for holding the standard when it matters most.

Clara Hawking, UK and Europe

AIEOU is a place where diverse voices are involved. Serpil Meri Yilan, UK and Europe

AIEOU truly builds community - you make belonging real and show how joyful and achievable collaboration can be. Thanks a lot AIEOU Team! Tuyet Ngo, UK and Asia

A Great Global Initiative!! AIEOU connects global educators and learners to learn, explore and share AI In Education. Mukesh Sharma

AIEOU has been an impactful community bringing together numerous nuanced voices from across the globe. The regular interactions on multiple platforms, be it blog, seminar, webinar have not just been interesting but also though provoking. I hope the community soon looks to publish a journal and a podcast. Wishing the community many more years of learning and joy. Rahul Pachori, India

Thank you for creating this wonderful community!

Alberto Garcia, UK and Europe

AIEOU has proven that the future of education isn't just about algorithms but it's about the people connecting to discuss them. Congratulations on a year of building bridges across borders and disciplines. Happy Birthday AIEOU!

Meltem Ipek Oner, Middle East

Being part of AIEOU has made me think about my practice and how to use AI safely within the classroom. It inspired me to create and put my thoughts into the world.

Gemma Keating, Asia and Oceania

Being part of the vibrant AIEOU community has been truly rewarding. Your commitment to learning, collaboration, and excellence continues to inspire all of us. Wishing you a wonderful birthday celebration and many more years of impact and success. Zohaib Khurshid

I wish AIEOU all the best for the forthcoming years. Indeed it's a much needed initiative. Mariam Shadan

AIEOU is an incredible global community that has elevated my expertise, grown my diverse connections, and created a supportive subgroup of women AI experts. Jaime Bissa, Americas

The AIEOU convening was an absolutely phenomenal event. I was able to connect with data scientists, policy makers, teachers, researchers, innovators. Those connections have proved to be invaluable already, collaborating on exploring the future of education.

Simon Balderson, UK and Europe

Happy Birthday AIEOU!

AIEOU has become a hub to meet colleagues, exchange ideas and learn from each other. I've appreciated the chance to learn from people I wouldn't have met otherwise. I hope to stay involved and offer more over time. Gökhan Hiniz, UK and Europe

It has been a pleasure to be part of AIEOU, presenting ideas relating to our new AI curriculum at Queen's College London. I'm looking forward to new opportunities through AIEOU over the next year and speaking more with the highly informed and interesting people I have met, through AIEOU. Natasha Fenwick, UK

AIEOU is not just a research community; it is a laboratory of ideas that expands my perspective and opens doors to meaningful collaborations. It has profoundly shaped the direction of my research on AI in special education, giving me both inspiration and the momentum to take action. I am truly grateful to be part of this journey, and I look forward with excitement to what we will build together. Cigdem Nilufer UMAR

This is a strong group of thinkers and doers who share the mission to bring great educational value through AI. The mixture of research, theory, practice and innovation is an engine of the future from which all stakeholders should feel the impact. Matthew Esterman

I've been on a journey to understand AI's role in education, and AIEOU Oxford reinforced how important it is to embrace innovation while addressing challenges. It inspired me to keep learning and collaborate to improve education. Paola Martinez Romero, UK and Europe

It was a wonderful experience being part of the great AIEOU community. I met so many inspiring people whose energy, ideas, and generosity gave me both the strength and the vision to move forward with even greater purpose. Each conversation opened a new perspective, and the collective passion in the room reminded me why collaboration and shared imagination are essential for shaping the future. Baris Atiker, UK and Europe

Being part of this community has genuinely supported my work and my growth. You've built a space where educators can learn from each other, ask real questions, and feel supported without judgment. I appreciate how practical, honest, and human the conversations are. It's a place where we can think, try, fail, try again, and keep moving forward together. I'm grateful to be here and proud to be part of what you're building. Andy Lucchesi, UK and Europe

Congratulations to AIEOU on its remarkable first year. AIEOU has been key in elevating my work through timely, ethical, and relevant support. Continuously, I am refining my AI skills and integrating them into education, enabling me to conduct virtual sessions in India and abroad and embed AI meaningfully into my regular teaching. I'm confident AIEOU will continue to grow, achieve new milestones, and expand its vibrant community. Rishi Raj Balwaria, Asia and Oceania

It's been wonderful being part of AIEOU community. Thank you for creating such an innovative, supportive and vibrant community. Amandeep Sehmi, Asia and Oceania

My heartfelt congratulations to the entire AIEOU fraternity on this special occasion. Happy Birthday, AIEOU!!! May the coming year be filled with bold ideas, inspiring research, meaningful collaborations, and groundbreaking discoveries. Sarah Javed

Happy Birthday AIEOU!

Happy Birthday 1 today!! AIEOU proud to be a part! Jonathan Kelly, Asia and Oceania

Great to be part of such an broad network.
Erdoğan Saçan, UK and Europe

AIEOU has been the first place I've found where practitioners and researchers are genuinely working on the same questions. The September conference gave me the push to start thinking seriously about turning my school's AI implementation work into formal research.
Chris Hack, UK and Europe

AIEOU is a community that brings research, practice and innovation together in a constructive, human-centred way. I'm grateful to be part of this network and excited for everything we will build together in the years ahead. Annabel Declercq

AIEOU's has connected educators from around the world to study and discuss one of the most urgent challenges facing society today. Gerald Crisci, Americas

AIEOU has created a vibrant global community of researchers passionate about AI in education. I'm proud to be part of this growing network driving innovation and equity in learning. Fatma Caner

Happy first birthday! I look forward to many more years of meaningful contribution.
Haeng A Kim

The AIEOU community are one of the most collaborative and forward-thinking groups in education. Lots of game-changing research at every meeting/webinar so far! A joy to be a (small) part of!
James Ahsan, UK and Europe

Happy birthday, AIEOU! Thank you for creating a rare space where AI in education is discussed with depth, evidence, and real openness. I left the conference feeling inspired, better informed, and connected to a brilliant community shaping responsible, high impact use of AI for learning.
Shiv Contractor, UK and Europe

Well done for bringing us all together!
Gaia Scerif, UK and Europe

It was a great year! I met many people and I am very proud that I was a presenter in an AIEOU webinar! Next year I hope to be in person in Oxford. IOANNIS ANAPLIOTIS, UK and Europe

Wonderful initiative with a visionary mission!
Antonis Mouhtaropoulos, UK and Europe

A vibrant community that is transforming education.
Jennifer Verschoor, Americas

Thank you. It's privilege being party of the community
Harvey Trump, Africa

Being part of AIEOU has been one of the most inspiring and productivity-enhancing experiences of my professional journey this year. The webinars offered throughout the year provided strong support for both my academic development and professional growth. I am truly grateful for all the moments of shared learning and collaboration, and for the multidimensional perspective this community has given me.
Happy Birthday, AIEOU! Özlem Esen

AIEOU has enabled me to collaborate with bold and critical thinkers who are shaping the future of AI in education. Happy birthday!
Simone Ries

Thank you, AIEOU, for being a space where ideas turn into action. Sultan Tutku Budak-Özalp

Happy Birthday AIEOU!

AIEOU provides rare access to genuinely interdisciplinary scholarship on AI in education. The network prioritises rigour over hype and creates space for researchers to challenge assumptions rather than adopt technology uncritically. This matters, particularly when the stakes involve real students, teachers, and the future of knowledge itself. Peter Bannister, UK and Europe

Being part of this community has been such an inspiring journey. Happy birthday! Here's to many more years of learning, growing, and creating impact together! Ezgi Aydemir Altaş, UK and Europe

AIEOU has not just been asking 'How AI can help education?' - It has been asking 'How can we educate humanity, the people who will live with AI, in this postdigital world?' That's the question that matters. A question that will help humankind to negotiate the emergent, complex human-technology entanglement. Kuda VJ Murombedzi, Africa

I think it's vital for people to be able to come together to explore thinking around AI in Education, and am very supportive of AIEOU's endeavour in this! Joanna Marriott, Africa

I am thankful to you for being a part of my AI world. Hayal Köksal

This was an absolute springboard for expanding the conversation and developing AI in Education. Matthew Wimpenny-Smith, UK and Europe

Education systems globally are on the cusp of a fundamental transformation. To successfully navigate this shift, the world requires a thoughtful and committed intellectual community to deliberate deeply on the future of AI in Education. AIEOU is precisely the promising start we needed to tackle this critical challenge. Mostafa Zabet, Middle East

Happy 1st Birthday, AIEOU! As a science educator being part of this global community has been incredibly inspiring. It empowers teachers like me to bridge the gap between advanced technology and classroom reality. Thank you for bringing us all together to shape the future of education!

Betül GÜZELKAYA

I appreciate the efforts made by AIEOU to bring teachers and researchers together and I look forward to engaging more actively in the near future.

Darina Slattery, UK and Europe

Thanks for all the research and thought provoking work you do.

Lovely learning with you

Jane Basnett, UK

Well done on a great, global initiative!

James Victor, Asia and Oceania

The AIEOU community delivers a broad spectrum of learning experiences that span different age groups and educational settings. As an international community, it benefits from diverse perspectives and contributions from various local communities, creating a rich, multifaceted knowledge base. I believe the AIEOU community will continue to foster greater knowledge sharing and collaboration in the future. Nuzra Afthah, Middle East

Happy first birthday, AIEOU! It's so great that you exist and bring so many people together. 😊

Luisa Baum, Europe

AIEOU has become one of the most engaging global communities in AI in education. It has enabled me to meet inspiring colleagues, sparked the ideas, and brought to my mind that collaboration is the key to shaping responsible and human-centered AI for learners around the world. Happy birthday.

Mahmoud Hawamdeh, Middle East

Happy Birthday AIEOU!

I'm deeply impressed by AIEOU and its unwavering commitment to connecting educators and stakeholders worldwide, and to providing a meaningful platform for sharing and advancing AI in education. Thank you, Dr Sara Ratner and team, for your steadfast support and inspiring leadership. May your work continue to inspire the global community for many years to come. Happy Birthday! Lydia Foong, Asia and Oceania

I have just joined this wonderful community, the webinars I attended were interesting. It's a great initiative from Oxford, I hope it will foster more critical thinking and shared awareness of the true potential but also risks of AI in education. Happy birthday! ❤️ Hafssa Manar, Africa

AIEOU is generating vital energy in the educational research field and I am particularly excited for year two, when we will see the AIEOU Collab Labs come to life. This connecting of aspirational goals, ideas, thinkers, researchers, and practitioners to help shape the an agenda for progress in AI in Education is thrilling. Mary Lang, Americas

Happy happy Birthday! I love how this precious child is growing wings and spreading its influence far and wide, touching and impacting lives positively! Meesha Arora

Happy 1st Birthday, AIEOU! It's been inspiring to see how this community has brought people together across the world to share ideas about AI in education! Cheers!! Louie Gira, Asia and Oceania

AIEOU is a beacon to guide educationists and learners in rapidly evolving education landscape. Farrukh Hafeez

Collaboration strengthens our understandings of AI and encourages critical conversations to fosters new ways of thinking and being. The AIEOU community provides a valuable platform to share and create ideas. Tara Solomon, Asia and Oceania

Thank you for connecting me with fabulous new colleagues Elizabeth Brown, UK

Happy birthday AIEOU !

Over the past year, you've grown a large family through numerous seminars and events. I hope you'll add new members to your family in the future and leave a positive impact on the world. I appreciate your efforts to enrich my journey in artificial intelligence and to better equip me in this discipline. With great gratitude, I wish you many more years. Happy happy birthday 🎂 🍌 🍷 🌸 🍷 Ülkü ÜLKER, UK and Europe

AIEOU has achieved something genuinely rare in AI and education: you've shifted the conversation from fear to possibility... from what we're afraid AI might do to what our systems could become if we get this right. In just twelve months, you've shown what's possible when educators, technologists and policy thinkers come together to design AI with purpose, humility and a deep respect for learning and equity. Here's to the work ahead and to the future you're helping us imagine. Michelle Michael, Australia

AIEOU has created a space where people working on AI in education can actually find each other, compare notes, and spark new ideas. It's still early days, but even in its first year it's already nudged a handful of meaningful collaborations into existence. I'm excited to see how it grows into the kind of global community the field really needs. Gary Liang, Asia and Oceania

Happy Birthday AIEOU!

Congratulations to AIEOU! And I am proud to be involved in this meaningful initiative. Looking forward, I wish to continue the impactful work with people from around the world to advance AI in Education!
Chun Wang (Reinhard) Chau, Asia and Oceania

An inspiring and thought provoking community. A great networking space. Thank you!
Marcin Kleban, UK and Europe

Great platform, lot of regional associations have formed. Happy to see in short time AIEOU have conducted several different activities, webinars, Conference and knowledge sharing sessions.
Hasnain Zafar Baloch, Asia and Oceania

Presenting at the inaugural convening was a professional highlight of 2025. The depth of conversation regarding 'human-centered values' and equity has been instrumental in how we are designing AI readiness programs for our colleagues in Istanbul. Thank you to the organizers for creating such a critical, constructive space. A huge thank you to Dr. Sara Ratner and the team for gathering over 100 global collaborators to explore the future of AI. The focus on educators as 'curators of learning experiences' resonated deeply with me. It was an honor to be part of the conversation, and I look forward to seeing this community grow!
Züleyha Tulay

Happy Birthday, AIEOU!
Thanks to the awesome community and space for learning, sharing, and innovation.
AIEOU - Always onward and upward.
Wishing many more milestones of impact!
Priyadarshini Muthukrishnan

¡¡ Feliz Cumpleaños AIEOU !!
Jose Fernandez-Calvo

Keep going — your work really means something, and it shows.
Alireza Chamanzar, Middle East

Happy first birthday to AIEOU! It's exciting to contribute to a global community around responsible, human-centred AI in learning. Looking forward to what we build together next!
Bert Verhoeven, Asia and Oceania

The global platform, AIEOU provided by the University of Oxford is a powerful catalyst, legitimizing the need for sophisticated AI education and opening doors for educators to contribute to and benefit from international research. This collaboration offers a path for us to bridge the AI literacy gap, even to 3rd World Countries where I live, equipping a new generation with the tools that are human centered through a design thinking strategy of continued collaboration.
Ruston Ocampo Banal, Asia and Oceania

Celebrating a year of meaningful conversations, collaboration, and vision for responsible AI in Education. Excited for what's ahead!
Anait Akopyan, UK and Europe

It is an amazing community. It is inclusive, open and with a very inspiring and encouraging atmosphere.
Lecky Li, UK.

AIEOU is an important initiative which provides a space for critical discussions around the implementation of AI in education.
Rob Farrow

Happy First Birthday, AIEOU! In one year, you've created an impactful global hub for dialogue and collaboration on AI in education. I look forward to continuing being part of this growing community and am excited to witness how our collective efforts will contribute to shaping ethical and innovative teaching and learning practices in schools and universities everywhere.
Dr. Carmen J. Civdanes-Lago

Happy Birthday AIEOU!

Joining AIEOU has enabled me to explore various AI research materials, connecting with people across the globe, and leveraging the potential of growing my research in AI.

Grace Ogechukwu Ugwonna, Africa

A great group working on the use of artificial intelligence in education, which will shape the future, and the dissemination of ethical values. It's a great feeling to be part of this group. Happy birthday AIEOU! Gülhan Arslan

Thank you so much AIEOU community! I believe what is special about the AIEOU is that it is a global inclusive community of practice; it has brought together so many different people across the world with a shared love of education and curiosity about generative AI. While we might all have different thoughts and apply different methodologies in how we understand AI in education, AIEOU has provided a platform for us to engage in collegial discussion and research, and test out our thoughts in a safe space.

Olivia Inwood, Asia and Oceania

The Oxford University AI Hub has been a source of inspiration, innovation, and meaningful learning. Its commitment to ethical, impactful AI and collaborative knowledge-sharing has empowered educators and researchers like me to rethink how technology can genuinely serve society. I am grateful for the Hub's vision, leadership, and the global community it continues to build. Wishing the Oxford University AI Hub a very happy birthday and many more years of transformative impact.

Asad Qayyum

Happy Birthday, AIEOU!

AIEOU is a rare space where innovation in AI and education is guided by human values. It shows how technology can serve learning, creativity, and human rights reminding us that the future of education must be not only intelligent, but also just and humane.

Srabonty Das Gupta, UK and Europe

Publishing my blog article "Code or Clicks?" with the AIEOU Hub was a deeply rewarding scholarly experience. The rigorous and constructive feedback I received significantly improved the clarity, structure, and depth of the final piece. I am particularly grateful to Dr. Sara Ratner for her thoughtful guidance, encouragement, and detailed comments, which significantly strengthened the argument. The Hub is an inspiring space to be part of, bringing together educators and researchers worldwide who are engaging seriously with the future of AI in education. The webinars are intellectually rich and often feel like quiet teaching masterclasses, offering valuable insights into both emerging technologies and pedagogy. I am thankful to the Hub for creating such a reflective and globally connected academic community. Mahipal Jadeja, Asia and Oceania

Listening to the expertise and experiences of educators from around the world in their use of AI has been invaluable. The insights that have been shared have really helped develop practice in our own institution.

Eleanor Overland, UK and Europe

AIEOU is building more than a community; it is shaping a movement. In a short time, it has brought together educators, researchers, and practitioners to engage critically and responsibly with AI in education. Its rapid growth reflects not hype, but trust; trust in thoughtful dialogue, ethical practice, and real impact. Happy Birthday to a community that is clearly helping define the future of AI in education. Syed Ali Tarek

Happy Birthday to my dear AIEOU team.

Thank you, Dr. Sara, for everything.

Hasna Syakh, Middle East

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